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Deliverable D2: Summary report on the design of low impedance standards (specifications: 1 m Ω to 10 Ω with arbitrary phase angles, 10 mHz to 5 kHz, target relative uncertainty 1 %).

Lead Partner: LNE

Involved Partners: CMI, RISE, METAS, LNE, PTB, HIOKI

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DELIVERABLE D2 DESIGN REPORT

Development of low impedance measurement standards

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I. Abbreviations

2TP – Two terminal pair connection

4TP – Four terminal pair connection

AC – Alternating current

ADC – Analogue to digital convertor/conversion

DAC – Digital to analog conversion/convertor

DC – Direct current

EIS – Electric Impedance Spectrum/Spectroscopy

RLC – General impedance meter (R-Resistance, L-Inductance, C-Capacitance)

II. Introduction

The European JRP-i25 project [1] aims to provide a metrological approach to characterize Lithium-ion batteries that have completed their first industrial life in electric vehicles and can be used for a second application, for example as an energy storage system. In order to do so, a set of low impedance calibration standards intended for calibration of RLC/EIS meter had to be developed. The general requirements for the developed standards were following:

- Nominal impedance value: a few $m\Omega$
- Frequency range: 10 mHz – 5 kHz
- Electrical current level: < 2 A
- Relative uncertainty: 1 %
- 4TP four-terminal-pair connection
- BNC connectors (for BT4560 impedance meters)

Several different approaches were used to fulfil the requirements in this project:

- i) LNE has developed a passive resistive measurement standard based on current shunt geometry.
- ii) CMI has developed reactance standard based on mutual inductor with DC bias source.
- iii) RISE has developed electronic simulators based on power operational amplifiers.
- iv) METAS has developed digital simulator based on ADC and DAC converters.

Particular designs will be described in the following text.

III. LNE passive resistive standard

In the next section, we will present the developed analytical model of the current shunt, the frequency response, drift and temperature coefficient measurement results.

3.1. Current shunt design

3.1.1. Presentation of the current shunt structure

The proposed current shunt is based on a resistive disk made of a resistive alloy placed on an insulating substrate and on a coaxial line made of an inner conductor and an outer conductor (shielding). The material of the resistive disk is typically *Evanohm* (copper alloy), and the resistive layer is placed on an insulating *Shapal* substrate. The inner conductor is connected electrically to the inner and outer conductors. The resistance of the shunt is then defined by the resistive disk. This latter is perpendicularly arranged to the inner conductor of the shunt. This part of the structure defined in 2 terminal-pair is illustrated in Fig. 1. Two N-Type connectors are welded to the inner conductor at both sides of the coaxial line: the first connector is used for injecting the input current and the other for measuring the output voltage. These connectors are placed in the same axis as the inner conductor of the coaxial line.

Fig. 1. Structure of the proposed current shunt defined in two terminal-pair.

The current shunt has a coaxial configuration (currents circulating in the inner and outer conductors are equal in magnitude and of opposite directions) that ensures immunity against external electromagnetic fields. The return current I_1 flowing in the outer conductor in the opposite direction and with an amplitude equal to the forward current circulating in the inner conductor (see Fig. 2). The current I_1 flows radially through the resistive disk. The geometry of the resistive disk and the distribution of the current allows reducing strongly its self inductance: a few aH (attohenry). The electrical output voltage U_2 is generally measured by a calibrated voltmeter at the output of the shunt between the central connector and the shield (see Fig. 2).

The voltage U_2 is the voltage measured across the resistive disk. Finally, the transfer impedance Z_{21} of the impedance matrix $[Z]$ defines the impedance of the current shunt Z_{Shunt} .

Fig. 2. Structure of the current shunt defined in two terminal-pair including input current and output voltage.

The geometrical dimensions of the resistive disk are chosen to obtain the desired resistance value for the current shunt. The internal and external radii of the disc are determined by a gold deposit constituting the contact electrodes on the disk. The choice of the alloy was made according to the electrical, thermal and mechanical characteristics of the materials. A nickel-chromium alloy called *Evanohm* was chosen among other selected alloys.

The resistive disk was built using the sputter deposition method. Different parameters influence the quality of the deposit: evaporation rate, single or multi-layer deposit and evaporation temperature [1]-[4]. A final thickness of 400 nm of *Evanohm* is deposited on a *Shapal* substrate. The chosen resistive alloy (*Evanohm*) ensures the desired resistance value and has a negligible skin effect: its skin thickness is 4 mm at 5 kHz. The skin thickness δ_{alloy} of the resistive alloy is expressed in meters by the following equation [5]:

$$\delta_{\text{alloy}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\omega \mu \sigma_{\text{alloy}}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi f \mu \sigma_{\text{alloy}}}} \quad (1.1)$$

Where:

f : frequency of the electromagnetic wave in Hz;

ω : pulsation in rad/s;

μ : Magnetic permeability of the resistive alloy in H/m;

σ_{alloy} : Electrical conductivity of the resistive alloy in S/m.

The low thickness (400 nm) of the resistive disk requires the use of a substrate: electrically insulating (to avoid changing the resistance value determined by the resistive alloy), thermally conductive (to evacuate the heat generated in the resistive alloy), thick enough (to easily handle the resistive disk and ensure stability over time of the resistance value) and mechanically machinable. The *Shapal* substrate (Aluminum Nitride) has high thermal conductivity ($100 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at 20°C), low electrical conductivity (5.6 S/m at 25°C) and is easily machinable.

Two mechanical flanges are used on the conductors of the coaxial line: one on the central conductor, the other on the shield. The mechanical flanges used are designed to place the resistive disk in the coaxial line perfectly (small mechanical tolerances of $\pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$) and to ensure positioning stability.

The resistive disk (mainly the hole machined into it) ensures the centred position of the inner conductor in relation to the outer conductor. This centring imposes very small mechanical tolerances on the hole machined in the resistive disk (the upper mechanical tolerance is $+0.01 \text{ mm}$ and the lower one is 0 mm) and on the pin of the inner conductor (the upper mechanical tolerance is 0 mm and the lower one is -0.1 mm). Brass has been selected for its mechanical strength ($65 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$). However, the shielding material (outer conductor) is copper for its high thermal conductivity ($395 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$).

Two commercial N-type female RF connectors are used to inject current and measure voltage (see Fig. 3). The conformity of the connectors used to the IEEE 287-2007 standard (revision of the IEEE 287-1968 standard) has been verified [6] and exhibits a 50Ω characteristic impedance.

Fig. 3. Illustration of the N-type female RF connector used.

An adapter box has been fabricated to convert the two terminal-pair coaxial device (with N-type connectors) in four terminal-pair (with BNC connectors). The BNC connectors are electrically insulated from the metallic box. This structure will facilitate the calibration of the RLC-meter. The adapter box has been manufactured so that the "high" and "low" connections of the inner and outer circuits are mutually at right angles to eliminate mutual inductance between them [7]. The principle of the adapter box is shown in Fig. 4. The BNC connectors of the voltage are placed near the output of the current shunt (2TP structure with N-type connectors) in order to minimize the influence of cables and connectors on the voltage

measurement. The Fig. 5 shows the final structure of the current shunt defined in four terminal-pair (with BNC connectors).

Fig. 4. Current shunt with the adapter box to convert a coaxial two terminal-pair device (with N-type connectors) in terminal-pair configuration (with BNC connectors).

Fig. 5. Final structure of the current shunt defined in four terminal-pair (with BNC connectors).

The effect of the adapter box is considered negligible on the current shunt impedance variation as a function of frequency. This effect has been evaluated and will be presented later. We will present the different parameters of the electrical model that can influence the impedance variation of current shunt defined in two terminal-pair (with N-type connectors). The analytical evaluation of these parameters allowed us to define mechanically the dimensions and the final geometry of the current shunt

3.1.2. Electrical resistance of the current shunt

3.1.2.1. DC electrical resistance of the resistive disk

We consider a resistive disk with external radius R_{Out} , internal radius R_{In} and alloy thickness t_{Alloy} . The resistive alloy is disposed on an insulating substrate of thickness t_{Sub} . The electrical resistance is defined between two radii $R_{OutGold}$ and R_{InGold} determined by a gold deposit on the resistive disk (see Fig. 6). The DC resistance of the disk is calculated according to the electrical resistivity ρ_{alloy} of the alloy and the geometrical dimensions by the following equation:

$$R_{disk} = \frac{\rho_{alloy}}{2\pi \cdot e_{alloy}} \ln \left(\frac{R_{OutGold}}{R_{InGold}} \right) \quad (1.2)$$

Fig. 6. Structure and realization of the resistive disk.

As previously mentioned, the skin effect in the resistive alloy can be neglected up to 5 kHz (even a few MHz). The resistive disk has been designed with internal R_{InGold} and external $R_{OutGold}$ radii equal to 40 mm and 45 mm respectively. The thickness of the resistive disk (t_{Alloy}) is equal to 400 nm, the DC resistance of the resistive disk is equal to 17.5 m Ω at 23 °C.

3.1.3. Current shunt loss resistances

In the frequency bandwidth of interest (up to 5 kHz), the dielectric losses in the coaxial sections are neglected. Losses are modelled only by the resistance r_{Losses} : this represents the losses by Joule effect in the conductors of each coaxial section [5]. The Fig. 7 represents a coaxial section of the current shunt. The linear value of the losses resistance r_{Losses} is given as a function of the length of the coaxial section l , the radii R_{In} and $R_{Out,1}$ and the surface resistance $R_{S_Outer\ conductor}$ and $R_{S_Inner\ conductor}$ of outer and inner conductors respectively, it is calculated by:

$$r_{Losses} = \frac{l}{2\pi} \left(\frac{R_{S_Inner\ conductor}}{R_{In}} + \frac{R_{S_Outer\ conductor}}{R_{Out,1}} \right) \quad (1.3)$$

Fig. 7. Parameters of a coaxial section of the current shunt.

The inner and outer conductors are made of brass and copper respectively. The surface resistances $R_{S_Outer\ conductor}$ and $R_{S_Inner\ conductor}$ are then calculated according to the electrical conductivity σ_i of the conductive material (copper or brass) in the coaxial section and the skin thickness δ_s of the conductive material is given by the following equation:

$$R_s = \frac{1}{\sigma_i \delta_s} \quad (1.4)$$

The skin thicknesses of brass and copper at 5 kHz are 2 mm and 1 mm respectively. The skin effect impact in the conductive parts has been estimated through the values of the loss resistances r_{Losses} of the current shunt structure. The calculated values are lower than the resistance of the resistive disk: they are less than 27.7 nΩ. Therefore, the loss resistances influence is negligible.

3.1.4. Electrical inductance of the current shunt

3.1.4.1. Inductances of the resistive disk

The resistive disk is considered as the section of a transmission line with two planes A and B whose electric potential is different [8]-[10]. The Fig. 8 shows the transmission line network considered. The disk, considered as a 4-access network, is flowed by a radial electric current. The resistive disk is passive and symmetrical, we can then simplify the terms of its impedance matrix by: $Z_{11_disk} = Z_{22_disk}$ and $Z_{12_disk} = Z_{21_disk}$. Thus, it is only necessary to determine the input impedance Z_{11_disk} and the transfer impedance Z_{21_disk} to obtain the complete impedance matrix of the resistive disk. The Fig. 9 illustrates the electrical model of the resistive disk deduced from this system of equations.

Fig. 8. Resistive disk (red part) including input - output currents and voltages.

Fig. 9. Equivalent electrical model of the resistive disk.

The imaginary part of Z_{11_disk} is defined as an inductive component. The inductance at the input of the plane A (and the plane B) of the resistive disk is represented by the inductance L_{disk} :

$$L_{disk} = \frac{R_{disk} t_{alloy}^2 \mu \sigma_{alloy}}{3} \quad (I. 5)$$

The inductance M_{disk} represents the imaginary inductive part of the impedance Z_{21_disk} :

$$M_{disk} = -\frac{R_{disk} t_{alloy}^2 \mu \sigma_{alloy}}{6} = -\frac{L_{disk}}{2} \quad (I. 6)$$

Considering the geometrical dimensions and electrical conductivity of the resistive disk (2.73×10^6 S/m), the absolute values of the inductances L_{disk} and M_{disk} of the resistive disk are respectively equal to 1.7×10^{-19} H and 8.4×10^{-20} H. The effect of these values is thus negligible on the current shunt impedance variation up to a few kHz (some 5.3 fΩ at 5 kHz).

3.1.4.2. Inductances of the coaxial section

The inductance of the different coaxial sections represents the most important inductive component of the current shunt. The coaxial inductance value is given as a function of the external and internal radii (R_{In} and R_{Out_1}) of the coaxial section and the relative magnetic permeability μ_r of the insulating material [5] by:

$$L_{coax} = l \frac{\mu_0 \mu_r}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{R_{Out_1}}{R_{In}} \right) \quad (1.7)$$

Where:

- μ_0 the vacuum permeability or magnetic constant ($4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg.m.A}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-2}$);
- l length of individual sections of the coaxial part.

The perpendicular position of the resistive disk minimizes significantly the influence of this inductive component on the impedance Z_{21} of the impedance matrix $[Z]$ and thus on the impedance of the shunt Z_{shunt} . The values of L_{coax} are between 22 fH and 5.2 nH. The sum of the coaxial inductances of the current injection and voltage measurement sides are respectively equal to 15.4 nH and 11.9 nH.

3.1.5. Electrical capacitance of the current shunt

In the proposed structure, we consider three types of electrical capacitance as shown in Fig. 10. The three types of capacitance are:

- Coaxial capacitance C_{coax} calculated as a function of the different coaxial sections according to the different coaxial dimensions and material properties of the current shunt.
- Capacitance between the disk (or flange) and the shielding (outer conductor) in the disk area in contact with the flange (via the gold layer), there are three such capacitances:
 - C_{p1} : electrical capacitance between the flange and the part of the shielding on the current injection side (see Fig. 10).
 - C_{p2} : electrical capacitance between the gold deposit and the part of the shielding on the current injection side (see Fig. 10).
 - C_{p3} : electrical capacitance between the resistive disk (part in contact with the gold layer) and the part of the shielding on the electrical voltage measurement side (see Fig. 10).
- Capacitance disk-shield, this type is presented by two capacitances:
 - C_{g1} : electrical capacitance between the resistive disk outside the gold deposit and the part of the shielding on the electric current injection side (cf. Fig. 10).
 - C_{g2} : electrical capacitance between the resistive disk outside the gold deposit and the part of the shielding on the measurement side of the electrical voltage (see Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Different types of electrical capacitances in the current shunt structure.

3.1.5.1. Capacitance of the coaxial section

This capacitance value in the different coaxial sections depends on the external and internal radii of the coaxial section (R_{In} and R_{Out_1}) and on the relative permittivity of the dielectric (ϵ_r) (see Fig. 10). The linear capacitance C_{coax} is calculated by the following equation [5]:

$$C_{coax} = \frac{2\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_r}{\ln\left(\frac{R_{Out_1}}{R_{In}}\right)} l \quad (1.8)$$

Where:

- ϵ_r relative permittivity of the dielectric in the coaxial part;
- ϵ_0 permittivity of free space;
- l length of individual sections of the coaxial part.

The sum of the coaxial capacitances of the current injection and voltage measurement sides are respectively equal to 2.5 pF and 2.4 pF.

3.1.5.2. Electrical capacitance between the resistive disk and the shielding (outside the flange)

For the proposed current shunt, we have two plane electrical capacitances due to the interaction between the resistive disk and shielding faces (see Fig. 10): C_{g1} (defined between the resistive disk and the shielding part on the current side) and C_{g2} (defined between the resistive disk and the shielding part on the voltage measurement side). The electrical

capacitances are considered in parallel with the coaxial capacitances of the shunt. This type of capacitances C_{gk} (with $k = 1$ or 2) is calculated by the following equation [11]:

$$C_{gk} = \frac{2\pi \varepsilon_r \cdot \varepsilon_0 \cdot R_{OutGold}^2}{d \cdot \text{Ln}^2 \left(\frac{R_{OutGold}}{R_{InGold}} \right)} \left[\frac{1}{4} - \frac{2 \cdot R_{InGold}^2}{R_{OutGold}^2} \left(\text{Ln}^2 \left(\frac{R_{OutGold}}{R_{InGold}} \right) + \text{Ln} \left(\frac{R_{OutGold}}{R_{InGold}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (I. 9)$$

Analytically, we have considered that the electrostatic fields defining the capacitances C_{g1} and C_{g2} are superposed with the electrostatic fields defining the coaxial capacitances of the same coaxial sections. The total capacitance of the last sections is calculated by the sum of all capacitances calculated separately. The analytical values of the capacitances C_{g1} and C_{g2} are equal respectively to 0.3 pF and 5.8 pF. The values obtained are very low and does not influence the frequency variation of the current shunt impedance up to some kHz.

3.1.5.3. Electrical capacitance between the resistive disk and the shielding (outside the gold deposit)

The electric field between the gold deposit or flange and the shielding is uniform because the electric potential is constant over the entire surface of the flange. As previously in the expressions of the capacitances C_{g1} and C_{g2} , we have in the current shunt structure three electrical capacitances (see Fig. 10): C_{p1} , C_{p2} and C_{p3} . The expression of the capacitance C_{pk} (with $k = 1$ to 3) is determined as a function of :

- the surface area S of the two armatures defining the cross-section studied,
- the distance d (d_{flange} , d_{gold} and t_{sub} respectively for C_{p1} , C_{p2} and C_{p3}) between these two armatures
- the nature of the dielectric.

The value of C_{pk} is estimated by the following simplified equation [5]:

$$C_{pk} = \frac{\varepsilon_r \cdot \varepsilon_0 \cdot S}{d} \quad (I. 10)$$

The values of the capacitances C_{p1} , C_{p2} and C_{p3} are respectively equal to 0.1 pF, 6.7 pF and 0.1 nF.

3.2. Current shunt measurements

3.2.1. Frequency variation of current shunt impedance

Two parameters are essentially used to characterize the impedance frequency variation:

- The frequency variation of the impedance magnitude compared to the DC value (AC-DC difference) generally given by:

$$\delta = \frac{R_{DC} - |Z_{shunt}|}{R_{DC}} \quad (I. 11)$$

Where, R_{DC} is the DC resistance of the developed current shunt.

- The phase angle defined as:

$$\Delta\varphi = \arctan\left(\frac{\Im[Z_{shunt}]}{\Re[Z_{shunt}]}\right) \quad (I. 12)$$

Where:

$\Im[Z_{shunt}]$ is the imaginary part of the shunt impedance;

$\Re[Z_{shunt}]$ is the real part of the shunt impedance.

AC-DC difference and phase angle are measured for the current shunt developed at 1 A and 2 A for the frequencies: 53 Hz, 1 kHz and 5 kHz. The experimental setup used is called MSD (Phase-shifted signal measurers), its principle is presented below.

3.2.1.1. Presentation of the measurement system

The measurement system used is a phase angle measurement system for sinusoidal voltage (10 mV to 1 000 V) with frequency range from 20 Hz to 20 kHz. Its principle is based on a sampling method with a least squares sine fit algorithm (see Fig. 11). This measurement system has been adapted for AC resistors comparisons. The automated reference setup ensures uncertainties less than 250 $\mu\Omega/\Omega$ and 5 mrad respectively on the amplitude and phase of the AC resistors between 10 m Ω and 1 M Ω for a frequency range up to 20 kHz.

Fig. 11. Calibration set up for the measurements of AC resistances at LNE .

3.2.1.2. The influence of the adapter box to convert the current shunt from 2TP to 4TP

The current shunt developed is measured with and without the adapter box. The shunt was measured for a current of 2 A for the following frequencies: 53 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 3 kHz, 4 kHz and 5 kHz. The Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 shows the AC-DC difference and the phase angle at 2 A without and with the adapter box, respectively.

Fig. 12. AC-DC difference at 2 A of the developed current shunt without and with the adapter box.

Fig. 13. Phase angle at 2 A of the developed current shunt without and with the adapter box.

The AC-DC difference without and with the adapter box is less than 1.3 m Ω/Ω and 1.0 m Ω/Ω respectively. The absolute values of the phase angle without and with the adapter box is less

than 0.2 mrad and 0.8 mrad respectively. Considering the measurement uncertainties, we can neglect the adapter box effect on the variation of the current shunt impedance as a function of frequency.

3.2.1.3. AC-DC difference of the current shunt

The developed current shunt has been characterized using the MSD bench at 1 A and 2 A for the frequencies: 53 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 3 kHz, 4 kHz and 5 kHz. The AC-DC difference at 1 A and 2 A up to 5 kHz is less than: $1.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ m}\Omega/\Omega$ ($k=2$). The Table I shows the measurement results. The Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 shows the AC-DC difference at 1 A and 2 A of the developed current shunt.

Table I. AC-DC difference of the developed current shunt.

Current level (A)	Frequency in kHz	Measure of 05 October 2020		Measure of 12 March 2021	
		AC-DC difference δ in $\text{m}\Omega/\Omega$	Uncertainty $u(\delta)$ in $\text{m}\Omega/\Omega$ ($k = 2$)	AC-DC difference δ in $\text{m}\Omega/\Omega$	Uncertainty $u(\delta)$ in $\text{m}\Omega/\Omega$ ($k = 2$)
1	0,053	2×10^{-4}	0.49	3×10^{-7}	0.49
	1	0.23	0.47	0.63	0.48
	2	0.95	0.47	0.94	0.47
	3	0.99	0.47	0.98	0.47
	4	1.24	0.47	1.03	0.47
	5	1.28	0.48	1.39	0.47
2	0,053	3×10^{-4}	0.57	1×10^{-6}	0.48
	1	0.36	0.54	0.48	0.47
	2	0.82	0.58	0.79	0.47
	3	0.91	0.57	0.98	0.47
	4	0.92	0.61	0.89	0.47
	5	0.83	0.52	0.82	0.47

Fig. 14. AC-DC difference at 1 A of the developed current shunt.

Fig. 15. AC-DC difference at 2 A of the developed current shunt.

3.2.1.4. Phase angle of the current shunt

The same measurement bench was also used to characterize the phase angle. The absolute value of the phase angle at 1 A and 2 A up to 5 kHz is less than: 1.1 ± 0.9 mrad ($k=2$). The Table II shows the measurement results. The Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 shows the phase angle at 1 A and 2 A of the developed current shunt.

Table II. Phase angle of the developed current shunt.

Current level (A)	Frequency in kHz	Measure of 05 October 2020		Measure of 12 March 2021	
		Phase angle $\Delta\phi$ in mrad	Uncertainty $u(\Delta\phi)$ in mrad ($k = 2$)	Phase angle $\Delta\phi$ in mrad	Uncertainty $u(\Delta\phi)$ in mrad ($k = 2$)
1	0.053	0.32	0.89	-0.03	0.89
	1	-0.08	0.89	-0.09	0.89
	2	-0.21	0.89	-0.22	0.89
	3	-0.28	0.89	-0.16	0.89
	4	-0.70	0.89	-0.27	0.89
	5	-1.03	0.89	-0.32	0.89
2	0.053	0.35	0.82	0.09	0.82
	1	-0.11	0.82	-0.15	0.82
	2	-0.25	0.82	-0.34	0.82
	3	-0.41	0.82	-0.46	0.82
	4	-0.48	0.82	-0.58	0.82
	5	-0.96	0.82	-0.84	0.82

Fig. 16. Phase angle at 1 A of the developed current shunt.

Fig. 17. Phase angle at 2 A of the developed current shunt.

3.2.2. Drift of the current shunt

The drift of the current shunt (DC resistance stability as a function of time) is an important parameter to be characterized. This is obtained by measuring, at a constant temperature, the DC resistance of the current shunt as a function of time. The drift of the developed current shunt was measured with the measuring bench used at LNE to calibrate the DC resistances. The drift has been measured over few days to have an accurate estimation of the long term stability.

3.2.2.1. Presentation of the measuring bench

DC calibration of resistors and in particular of current shunts is based on a direct comparison method (see Fig. 18): comparison of the resistance to be calibrated (R_X) and the standard resistance (R_E). The ratio of the two resistances is equal to the ratio of the DC voltages U_E and U_X measured respectively at the terminals of R_E and R_X through which the same current I flows. The measuring bridge, previously calibrated, injects the current I and then measures the voltages U_E and U_X . The experimental setup used at LNE for DC resistance measurements is illustrated in the Fig. 19. The resistance value R_X is given by:

$$R_X = R_E \frac{U_X}{U_E} \quad (I. 13)$$

Fig. 18. Principle of the bench used at LNE for DC resistance measurements.

Fig. 19. Calibration set up for the measurements of DC resistances at LNE (uncertainty level 2).

3.2.2.2. Measurement of the current shunt drift

The current shunt is measured with LNE's measuring system for calibrating DC resistors for currents of 100 mA, 1 A and 2 A. The drift is calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Drift} = \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_0} \quad (\text{I. 14})$$

Where:

β_0 is the intercept of the linear regression of the DC resistance of the current shunt as a function of time;

β_1 is the slope of the linear regression of the DC resistance of the current shunt as a function of time.

The drift is repeated two times with a 6 months interval: the figures: Fig. 20, Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 presents the results obtained. The calculated drift value of the developed current shunt is less than 0.15 (mΩ/Ω)/day ($5.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$). This important value is mainly caused by the quality and the sputter deposition parameters (not optimized) of the deposited Evanohm layer

[11]. Therefore, before using the current shunt, it is necessary to calibrate the DC resistance and to wait for a heating time of the current shunt at the nominal electric current of approximately 15h. The DC resistance values are measured with an expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of $\pm 2 \mu\Omega$.

Fig. 20. Drift of the developed current shunt at 100 mA.

Fig. 21. Drift of the developed current shunt at 1 A.

Fig. 22. Drift of the developed current shunt at 2 A.

3.2.3. Temperature coefficient measurement of the current shunt

The temperature coefficient (TC) of the shunt is measured in a thermal box to ensure a stable temperature: the stability of this box is in a few milli-degrees. The measurement bench (see Fig. 23) is composed of the thermal box, a control computer, a temperature sensor (platinum probe), a humidity sensor (capacitive sensor) and a multimeter (Fluke 8508A). The resistance measurement is carried out in 4 terminals. The temperature coefficient is calculated by the following equation:

$$TC = \frac{R_{DC}(T_1) - R_{DC}(T_2)}{R_{DC} (|T_1 - T_2|)} \quad (I. 15)$$

Where: R_{DC} , $R_{DC}(T_1)$ and $R_{DC}(T_2)$ are the DC resistances measured respectively at ambient temperature, temperature T_1 and temperature T_2 .

Fig. 23. Calibration set up for the measurements of the temperature coefficient measurement.

The temperature coefficient TC was measured by setting the temperature of the box to 18.5 °C, 20 °C, 21.5 °C, 23 °C, 24.5 °C, 26 °C and 27.5 °C. The temperature coefficient TC is calculated for nominal temperatures of 20 °C, 23 °C and 26 °C using the equation (I. 15). Table III shows the measured values of the temperature coefficient TC. The TC value of the developed current shunt is between 2.4 (mΩ/Ω).K⁻¹ and 2.8 (mΩ/Ω).K⁻¹. Considering the manufacturer's specifications, the TC calculated of Evanohm on the insulating substrate Shapal is 2.8 (mΩ/Ω).K⁻¹. The TC of the current shunt is thus equal to that of the resistive material deposited on the insulating substrate. Fig. 24 shows the DC resistance values of the developed current shunt as a function of temperature. The important value of the temperature coefficient TC is explained by the homogeneity of the deposited thin film, the sputter deposition parameters have not been optimized in this project to minimize the measured values. This important value will not influence the use of the current shunt for the multimeter calibration.

Table III. Measured temperature coefficient TC of the developed current shunt

Nominal temperature (°C)	20	23	26
Temperature range (°C)	[18.5-21.5]	[21.5-24.5]	[24.5-27.5]
Range of the DC resistance (mΩ)	[17.22 - 17.44]	[17.44 - 17.56]	[17.56 - 17.71]
Temperature coefficient TC ((mΩ/Ω).K ⁻¹)	2,7	2,4	2,8

Fig. 24. DC resistance values of the developed current shunt as a function of temperature.

3.3. Conclusion

The current shunt developed is characterized by its coaxial geometry. Its design was made to minimize its thermal heating and obtain a low impedance variation (less than 1%) up to 5 kHz. It is mainly composed of a resistive disk placed in a coaxial line whose end is connected to two N-type connectors: the first one to inject the current and the second one to measure the voltage. The structure is completed by an adapter box to convert the two terminal-pair coaxial device (with N-type connectors) to measure four terminal-pair (with BNC connectors). The value of the DC resistance of the current shunt has been defined at 17.5 mΩ for a current less than 2 A. The absolute values measured for of transposition deviation and phase angle are less than 1.4 mΩ/Ω and 1.1 mrad respectively for currents below 2 A and frequencies up to 5 kHz. These values obtained permit a current shunt impedance variation less than 0.23 % (for a target set at 1%). The variation of the impedance of the current shunt as a function of the frequency is important compared to the analytical calculation because of the parameters of the vacuum deposition. The sputter deposition parameters have not been optimized to minimize the drift, temperature coefficient TC and the non-homogeneity of the deposited thin film.

IV. CMI reactance standard

CMI task was to develop 4TP reactance standard based on the mutual inductors having integrated DC bias source. The idea of the standard is the main impedance element, the mutual inductors, is a passive linear component (no ferromagnetic core) and the DC bias source is designed in such a way it cannot affect the simulated impedance. Therefore, a unique possibility to check RLC meter's dependence on the applied DC bias voltages is enabled.

Following document briefly describes experimental design of capacitive reactance simulator based on mutual inductance. Additional details are shown in Imeko paper [12]. The simulator is designed for calibration of battery impedance spectroscopy analysers (EIS).

Fig. 25. Calibration Principle of capacitance simulator based on mutual inductance (Left), full coaxial connection (Right).

The goal of the design was to achieve large capacitive reactance with simulation of DC bias voltage roughly equal to lithium cell (around 4V). The standard must be able to withstand measurement current at least 1A AC and 1A DC (2.5A peak current in both polarities).

One of the simple ways of simulating reactance is mutual inductor which can be easily designed to exhibit mutual inductances in order of nanohenry to microhenry and to be able to carry high measurement currents. If the secondary winding polarity is inverted, the apparent four terminal impedance will appear as capacitive reactance to the EIS. The basic concept is shown in Fig. 25. Impedances Z_1 and Z_2 can be used to fine tune the apparent impedance, however they are not necessary.

Fig. 26. Principle of DC bias generator.

The challenging part of the design is however introduction of the DC bias voltage. It is not possible to simply insert high power DC source in series with mutual inductor, because its internal impedance would destroy properties of the impedance. It is also not reasonable to insert it just into the potential terminal, because then the EIS meter will see DC voltage between its Hcur and Hpot terminals. It may lead to fail indication or even damage of the EIS. So, an alternative solution shown in Fig. 26 was chosen. Two, tandem controlled sources were used. One, high power floating DC source capable to withstand the measurement current is connected in series with the Hcur terminal. This source does not have to be very accurate. A second floating DC source is placed in series with the Hpot terminal. This source carries almost no current, but should be accurate and low noise. Both sources are set to identical voltage, so the EIS meter will see near zero voltage difference between Hcur and Hpot terminals and at the same time will see necessary DC bias of the impedance.

4.1. Design of DC bias source

Circuit design of first prototype is shown in Fig. 27 or see GitHub source files [13]. The only complicated part of the design is the DC bias source. Both DC sources must be floating. For purposes of first prototype this was solved by using DC/DC converters. The current DC bias is supplied from a pair of 9V and 3V3 converters. This asymmetric supply was chosen to minimize power dissipation as the DC voltage range is 0 to 5V and the power opamp OPA548 needs at least some 3V reserve. The DC/DC converters outputs are filtered by low-ESR polymer caps. Care must be taken to not exceed maximum filter capacitance for particular converter to prevent regulator instability. The controlled DC source is based on power opamp OPA548. It is equipped by stabilizing network and the output is filtered by low-ESR capacitors. The opamp feedback is providing low output impedance for low frequencies, whereas the large output capacitance is providing low impedance for higher frequencies. The voltage of this source is generated by 12bit DAC connected via isolated I2C bus. Zero and gain are set by two trimmers. The whole source can be disabled by DC/DC converter enable inputs and in that case a pair of parallel latching relays bypasses the output of the source.

Fig. 27. Circuit diagram of impedance simulator prototype.

The second source inserted to the potential terminals is of similar concept except it is supplied from low noise DC/DC converter with low noise LDO regulators and uses low power opamp OP211. Its output is also equipped by stabilizing network and the opamp and stabilizing network components must be chosen so it is stable with large output capacitance.

The standard itself (mutual inductor) is placed in separate box. It is connected via additional board with few latching relays that enables switching the polarity and range of the mutual inductor.

The whole unit is controlled by microcontroller AVR ATmega88. It is equipped by simple user interface with buttons and LED diodes and also it is connected to USB-UART converter MCP2200 for remote control. Note the MCP2200 is connected via optoisolator which inverts

UART polarity, so MCP2200 configuration utility must be used to invert polarity of UART outputs.

The unit contains electronically switchable fan outputs with regulation of speed using Zener diodes. One diode is intended to be used for idle speed and the other switchable for high speed when current path DC bias is enabled.

4.2. Construction notes

Board drawings are shown in Fig. 28 and Fig. 29 and at GitHub [13]. The DC source unit was designed to fit in Hammond die cast box HM-1550F. The power opamp OPA548 is soldered from bottom of the PCB, so its terminals must be bent up from the heatsink. It is screwed to the heatsink which is screwed from bottom of the PCB. The heatsink must be able to cool full power which is up to some 23W, so the fans are intended to be used.

The standard itself was placed to another box Eddystone 26908PSLA together with the relay board. Both boxes are connected via BNC connectors and Cannon 9 connector. The output terminals to the EIS are placed at the standard box. The connection between the two boxes is made using 3D printed components which are also available at GitHub [1]. Note there are no male BNCs with crimping terminals, so a flange types were used and they are connected to the coaxes via brass foil screwed to them.

The mutual inductor itself is constructed as air-core toroid so most of the field is contained. Therefore, it is not affected by near metallic objects and exhibits no significant non-linearities. The winding is made from multifilar rope of copper enamelled wires. 10 wires from the rope are connected in parallel and used as primary. The remaining 10 are connected in series to form secondary. The unit has two ranges, so one range is full 10 loops and the other range is connected to a first tap. The core of the toroid is 3D printed. See GitHub for model.

Fig. 28. Top layer of PCB.

Fig. 29. Bottom layer of PCB.

Fig. 30. Dual DC bias source main PCB. Note the power opamp OPA548 mounted from bottom side of PCB to the heatsink.

Fig. 31. Heatsink mounting at bottom of main PCB.

Fig. 32. Complete setup. Left: DC bias sources, right: mutual inductor with terminals to EIS.

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Fig. 33. Separate box with mutual inductor.

Fig. 34. Detail of toroidal mutual inductor.

4.3. Firmware

The firmware for the MCU is available at GitHub. It was made in AVR Studio 4 with AVRGCC compiler. Note the unit expects operation from internal RC oscillator set to 1 MHz which is default fuse setting, so no fuses should be modified. Programming is possible only via ISP interface. It is recommended to supply the unit from regulated PSU just in case the latching relays controller is “confused” during the programming via the shared SPI interface.

4.4. Remote operation

Remote interface is set to baud rate of 9600bd, 1 stop, no parity and no flow control. It implements few basic SCPI style commands. All commands and answers are terminated by LF. Chaining by semicolon is supported. Do not exceed 127 characters in long chained commands. Errors are returned using common SYST:ERR? command.

Command	Description
*IDN?	Returns identification string.
*RST	Resets device.
*OPC?	Returns +1 when device is ready.
SYST:ERR?	Returns last error (buffer can take only one error).
SYST:BOOT <passcode>	Invoke bootloader. Passcode = 17IND10. This command will jump to AVR microcontroller boot section as set by fusebits. If no bootloader was programmed, it will only reset device. See text for further details.
FAN <speed>	Sets FAN speed to HI/HIGH or LO/LOW (default powerup is LO).
MODE <mode>	Sets polarity of the secondary coil to „CAP“ or „IND“.
RANGE <range>	Sets range to „1“ or „2“.
COMMON:STATE <state>	Sets state of relay that connects current and potential terminals. Valid values are „0“, „OFF“ or „1“, „ON“.
POWER:STATE <state>	Enables or disables current DC bias source. Valid values are „0“, „OFF“ or „1“, „ON“.
BIAS:VOLT <level>	Sets both sources to identical level in millivolts. Note <level> is integer.
BIAS:POT:VOLT <level>	Sets level of potential DC bias source in millivolts. Note <level> is integer.
BIAS:PWR:VOLT <level>	Sets level of current terminal DC bias source in millivolts. Note <level> is integer.

4.5. Bootloader

Project also contains simple bootloader made in assembly code. It fits to last 512 Bytes of AVR FLASH memory. So bootsize fuse bits should be set accordingly (BOOTSZ1 = 1, BOOTSZ0 = 0). Eventually BOOTRST = 0 will make AVR jump to bootsection after powerup. For details see either bootloader ASM code or Octave bootloader m-file (both attached at GitHub [13]).

4.6. Known issues

The simulator is just a proof-of-concept prototype, so there are few problems that must be addressed for final version. First, the chosen DACs exhibit relatively high noise. They should be replaced by low noise types (eg. AD5781) or maybe at least equipped by low noise references.

Second, the DC/DC converters produce considerable common mode noise and also have large mutual capacitance. Both problems can be addressed by active guarding. The simplest way would be to connect two DC/DC converters in series and supply the join between them from a guard buffer. That will break capacitance to supply and should also reduce the noise. At the same time the guard buffer should guard the whole DC source part of the PCB and in case of the current path source it should also guard the heatsink somehow to reduce the capacitance as much as possible.

FW should be improved to be more SCPI compliant. Especially chaining commands by semicolon should be implemented.

4.7. Usage

Power supply:

The unit is designed for supply source 24 V, 1 A. Actual consumption depends on measurement current and will be much lower when current path bias source is disabled.

Fig. 35. Controls of the prototype.

Bias control:

Front panel of prototype is shown in Fig. 35. Pressing button “Bias” will cycle preset values of DC bias voltage to the shown levels. It is recommended to cycle through once around before connecting the unit to RLC meters just in case there is random voltage after power up glitch! When the “Cur. bias” LED is not lid, the current path bias source is inactive and shorted. Only the potential path bias source is driven, so the “Bias” button affects only potential path. When current path bias source is to be used, press button “Cur. bias”. LED will be lid and the simulator will be ready in few seconds once its internal DCDC converters charges filtration capacitors. When “Cur. bias” is lid, the “Bias” button will control both potential and current path bias sources and sets them to the same level.

Current-potential joint control:

Button “Com. GND” will connect potential and current paths together at low side. Always use this option for RLC/EIS meters, because otherwise they will not be able to balance! Not enabled “Com. GND” is suitable only for some specialized sampling bridges where balancing is not used, but it will change value of simulated impedance slightly.

Range and mode control:

Remaining controls are “Range” and “Mode”. The “Range” changes tap of the coil in the standard itself. Prototype contains coil with ranges roughly 350 nH “Lo” and 3.5 μ H “Hi”. Button “Mode” changes polarity of the secondary coil to simulate either inductive reactance “L” or capacitive reactance “C”. The reactance will change sign for both real and imaginary components, so do not be surprised the EIS meter will show negative loss tangent (or ESR) for capacitive mode.

Remote control:

As described above, the simulator has interface for remote control using few SCPI commands. Their function is equivalent to the buttons with one exception. It is possible to control independently potential and current path DC bias levels and it is possible to set any DC bias between 0 and 5 V. In that case LEDs “0V” and “5V” will be lid together to indicate remotely set levels. Pressing “Bias” will cancel this mode and set common level to both sources again. FAN speed can be increased which may be good idea when using current bias at full current.

Connection to RLC meters:

The unit was designed mainly for testing impedance analyzers for battery impedance spectroscopy (EIS). This simulator uses topology where bias voltage generators will not affect simulated impedance, so it offers unique possibility to check if the EIS meter is insensitive to applied bias. However, both current and potential sources can deliver significant power and both sources have large decoupling capacitances, so when connected to RLC meters that cannot stand external DC bias, such as Keysight E4980A, it may easily damage it! So be very cautious before connecting it to any RLC meter. Always check user manual. Some RLC meters may support external DC bias with external adapters, some may support it directly. It was tested directly with E4980A without any adapters, but before that it was necessary to disable “Cur. bias”, set “Bias” to “0V” and use multimeter to check there is actually no significant voltage between live conductors of potential and current BNCs! There will be always few millivolts, but that should be ok for most RLC meters.

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The simulator uses DCDC converters which inevitably produces considerable capacitive currents and EMC. Therefore, it is good idea to connect the simulator via coaxial cables equipped by coaxial chokes to reduce noise in the measurement. Four 500 mH chokes were used at ČMI for this purpose. Also connect negative power supply input to ground terminal of the RLC meter. This will improve the noise levels.

V. RISE low impedance standard

The aim of this work was to try to construct a low impedance standard (Limp) in a range typical for Li-ion battery cells. The standard should work in a frequency range of 10 mHz – 5 kHz, at rms current up to 1 A, and it should be stable within 0.1%.

The standard is an active circuit which simulates a 1 F capacitor using ceramic capacitors of 1 μF and a 10^6 -factor scaling circuit. By using ceramic capacitors, we can achieve higher stability and linearity compared with electrolytic capacitors, and the ceramic capacitors are ambipolar in contrast to electrolytic ones. While this demonstrator has only a single impedance value, it is quite straightforward to realise other values. If the 1 μF capacitor is replaced with a 1 k Ω resistor, the circuit will simulate 1 m Ω , a 10 μF capacitor will simulate 10 F, etc. This can be implemented as a small one port impedance which plugs into an external connector.

5.1. Measurements

The impedance of the Limp was measured by comparing it to a 100 A wideband current shunt with a nominal resistance of 8 m Ω in a digital complex impedance bridge. The voltage signals were measured with NI 5922 digitizers.

Below are the results of these measurements. The current used was 0.8 A rather than 1 A, because at some low frequencies the circuit became unstable after a few minutes, probably because of self-heating. At 0.8 A this was not a problem.

In the graphs, the measurement results (red rings) are compared with a model impedance of a capacitor and a resistor in parallel (black x'es). The model capacitor was 0.9678 F and the resistor was 0.9508 Ω . This gave a good fit for the absolute Limp value and a reasonable fit for the phase, up to about 1 kHz. Above 1 kHz there is a notable deviation, particularly in the phase. One should note, however, that the sampled output signal above 1 kHz was less than 100 μV , and we can expect a quite high uncertainty.

The parallel resistance of about 1 Ω comes from the fact that we connected the digitizer to the V2 output (see below), effectively putting the 1 M Ω input impedance of the digitizer in parallel to the 1 μF capacitance of the Limp. This 1 M Ω resistance was then scaled to 1 Ω in the scaling circuit.

Fig. 36. Modulus of impedance of RISE 1F standard. Red - measured, Black – simulated.

Fig. 37. Phase angle of impedance of RISE 1F standard. Red - measured, Black – simulated.

Frequency (Hz)	$ Z $ (Ω)	arg Z (rad)
0,01	9,4923E-01	-0,0551
0,015	9,4819E-01	-0,0825
0,02	9,4506E-01	-0,1094
0,03	9,3843E-01	-0,1636
0,05	9,1675E-01	-0,2683
0,07	8,8745E-01	-0,3675
0,1	8,3300E-01	-0,5026

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0,15	7,3358E-01	-0,6896
0,2	6,4014E-01	-0,8331
0,3	4,9330E-01	-1,0263
0,5	3,2520E-01	-1,2222
0,7	2,3924E-01	-1,3169
1	1,7022E-01	-1,3911
1,5	1,1448E-01	-1,4502
2	8,6141E-02	-1,4803
3	5,7556E-02	-1,5104
5	3,4575E-02	-1,5347
7	2,4701E-02	-1,5451
10	1,7293E-02	-1,5531
15	1,1531E-02	-1,5595
20	8,6492E-03	-1,5628
30	5,7658E-03	-1,5664
50	3,4595E-03	-1,5700
70	2,4713E-03	-1,5720
100	1,7299E-03	-1,5745
150	1,1532E-03	-1,5777
200	8,6470E-04	-1,5804
300	5,7655E-04	-1,5858
500	3,4671E-04	-1,5966
700	2,4801E-04	-1,6097
1000	1,7333E-04	-1,6269
1500	1,1537E-04	-1,6573
2000	8,3932E-05	-1,6439
3000	5,4123E-05	-1,6568
5000	2,9821E-05	-1,6086
7000	2,0963E-05	-1,4842
10000	2,0624E-05	-1,1485

Tab. 1. Measured complex impedance of RISE 1F standard.

5.2. Description of the circuit

Fig. 38. Circuit diagram of RISE 1F simulated impedance standard.

The two operational amplifiers (OP) and the resistors act as an impedance scaling circuit which scale the capacitors C1-C10 by a factor 10^6 . This means we can realise a virtual high value capacitor, in this case 1 F, with the stability and linearity of ceramic capacitors.

The U1 is a AD549 power OP because it needs to handle the input current up to 1 A, while the U2 is a AD8675 precision OP selected for its low noise properties. There are two output voltage ports which are nominally the same, but V1 is much noisier than V2, so normally V2 is preferable. However, the input impedance of the instrument measuring V2 will add in parallel to C1-C10 and will scale with the same factor. If, for example, an oscilloscope with a 1 M Ω

input impedance is connected to V2, the virtual impedance of the circuit will be 1 F in parallel with 1 Ω .

Resistors R1-R10 and R21-R30 are 10 Ω resistors in parallel, effectively 1 Ω , while R11-R20 and R31-R40 are 100 Ω resistors in series, effectively 1 k Ω . The parallel connection helps reduce stray inductance, while the series connection helps reduce stray capacitance, thereby improving the phase shift of the scaling circuit. The ratio 1 k Ω /1 Ω provide a scaling factor of -10^3 for each OP with a combined factor 10^6 . Capacitors C1-C10 are 100 nF in parallel, effectively 1 μ F, with an optional R41 resistor in parallel (not used). The trim resistor P41 (100 k Ω) is used to offset trim the entire circuit.

Since the OPs are feedback connected to both inputs, the circuit is prone to self-oscillation. A small input resistor R0 (100 m Ω) helps stabilise the circuit.

Two voltage regulators provide ± 5 V stable supply voltage to the OPs. They need at least ± 7 V input voltage.

5.3. Description of circuit board

Fig. 39. Printed circuit board layout of RISE simulated 1F standard.

The circuit board is a four-layer board, with the two inner layers used for the ± 5 V supply voltage from the voltage regulators, and the back side as well as part of the front serves as a ground plane. This improves the stability of the supply voltages by minimising the inductance and resistance of the supply leads. Care has also been taken to minimise stray inductances in the signal paths by using wide copper areas in low impedance parts of the circuit.

The circuit dissipates more than 10 W of power at 1 A input current, therefore several heat sinks are mounted on the board to keep the temperature of the components reasonably low. Two are mounted flat on the board next to the 10 Ω resistors at the input, one is mounted on the power OP and one on each of the voltage regulators.

Coaxial connectors on the board are used for input and output signals to minimise stray magnetic fields.

VI. METAS active digital impedance simulator

METAS developed digital impedance simulator “iSimulator”. Report attached in appendix no. 1 describes the working principle, the full characterisation and the results of the validation measurements of the iSimulator performed using a commercial LCR-meter (Keysight, Model E4980EL). The iSimulator has been designed to generate an apparent impedance with an arbitrary phase angle and with an amplitude from 1 m Ω to 10 Ω as required by the project. Though the iSimulator is supposed to work at lower frequency, it has been tested only down to 20 Hz, which is the smallest working frequency of the E4980EL instrument. While the highest frequency required by the project is 5 kHz, the iSimulator has been tested up to 10 kHz. The uncertainty on the gain error is smaller than the project’s target uncertainty of 1 % at low impedance value and is even smaller than 100 $\mu\Omega/\Omega$ for impedance value larger than 100 m Ω .

VII. List of appendices

No. 1 – Frédéric Overney, “Activity A1.2.3: Design Report: Impedance Simulator”.

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Appendix no. 1:

**Activity A1.2.3: Design Report: Impedance
Simulator**

Frédéric Overney

Activity A1.2.3: Design Report: Impedance Simulator

Frédéric Overney

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Abstract

This report is part of the **deliverable D2** of the project. It describes the working principle, the full characterisation and the results of the validation measurements of the iSimulator performed using a commercial LCR-meter (Keysight, Model E4980EL).

The iSimulator has been designed to generate an apparent impedance with an arbitrary phase angle and with an amplitude from 1 m Ω to 10 Ω as required by the project. Though the iSimulator is supposed to work at lower frequency, it has been tested only down to 20 Hz, which is the smallest working frequency of the E4980EL instrument. While the highest frequency required by the project is 5 kHz, the iSimulator has been tested up to 10 kHz.

The uncertainty on the gain error is smaller than the project's target uncertainty of 1 % at low impedance value and is even smaller than 100 $\mu\Omega/\Omega$ for impedance value larger than 100 m Ω .

1 Working Principle

The working principle of the impedance simulator (iSimulator) is represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Working principle of the the impedance simulator.

The device under test (DUT) is measuring the four terminal-pair impedance connected to its four connectors (HC , HP , LP and LC). The measured impedance Z_{DUT} is defined by the ratio of the voltage V measured at the input connector HP to the current I entering into the connector LC . The potential present at the connector LP being kept approximately to zero ('virtual ground'). The iSimulator consists into the connecting box (CB), directly connected to the four terminals of the DUT, and the PXI chassis hosting the required DACs and ADCs. Using the iSimulator, the current supplied by the DUT is flowing through the resistance Z_{CB} and returns to the DUT into the connector LC . The voltage drop V_i generated by the current through the resistance Z_{CB} is measured by a first digitizer and allows the precise determination of the the current $I = V_i/Z_{CB}$ supplied to the DUT. The voltage V measured by the DUT is supplied by the external source S_v and monitored at the level of the connector HP by a second digitizer. The reference impedance Z_{REF} is then determined from the measured voltage ratio $V_r = V_v/V_i$ and the calibrated impedance Z_{CB} .

Activity A1.2.2: report

Figure 2: Polar representation of the impedance Z_{DUT} and Z_{REF} .

The gain, G_{DUT} , of the DUT can then be evaluated by

$$G_{\text{DUT}} = \frac{Z_{\text{DUT}}}{Z_{\text{REF}}} = \frac{Z_{\text{DUT}}}{Z_{\text{CB}}V_{\text{r}}}, \quad (1)$$

and the **gain error** $g_{\text{DUT}} = |G_{\text{DUT}}| - 1$ as well as the **phase error** $\varphi_{\text{DUT}} = \angle G_{\text{DUT}}$ of the DUT are finally calculated. As represented in Fig. 2 the **measurement error** ΔR , expressed by the difference of the modulus of the two impedance values, can also be used instead of the gain error.

$$\Delta R = |Z_{\text{DUT}}| - |Z_{\text{REF}}|. \quad (2)$$

Both quantities are related each other by the relations $\Delta R = g_{\text{DUT}}|Z_{\text{REF}}|$ or $g_{\text{DUT}} = \Delta R/|Z_{\text{REF}}|$.

The unique ability of the iSimulator to change the amplitude and the phase of the voltage applied to the connector *HP* independently to the current entering into the connector *LC* allows the characterisation of the DUT over the whole complex plan using a single calibrated resistor Z_{CB} .

This version of iSimulator differs from that has been previously developed [1] in three main aspects:

- The current entering onto the *LC* connector is supplied by the DUT itself and not from and external source. In such a way the maximum current is not limited by the external source but by the DUT.
- The voltages V_{v} and V_{i} are simultaneously measured using two different digitizers instead to be successively measured by a single digitizer and a multiplexer. In such a way, the measuring time is divided by a factor of more than 2, limiting the overall time needed for the DUT characterisation, especially at low frequencies.

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- The residual voltage bias observed at the connector LP is taken into account for the correct evaluation of the current flowing through the resistance Z_{CB} . This is particularly important for simulating low impedance values.

Beside these differences, the working principle is very similar to that has been described in [1].

2 Design Description

2.1 Hardware

Figure 3 shows the global view of the measurement setup. The two key components that are the home-made connecting box and the NI-PXI 4461 board with the input and output channels and will be described in more details in the following subsections. The NI-PXI 4461 board is hosted in a PXI chassis NI-PXIE-1062Q.

Figure 3: View of the measuring setup with the device under test (DUT), the connecting box (CB) and the PXI chassis (PXI).

The 10 MHz master clock of the PXI-chassis is synchronised on an external 10 MHz supplied by signal synthesizer SRS DS 345. This 10 MHz frequency can be slightly biased (Δ_f) to ensure

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the coherency [2] between the frequency of the DUT's internal oscillator and the sampling frequencies used to generate S_V and to measure V_V and V_i .

A PXI-GPIB board allows the computer control of the DUT, making the whole measuring setup fully computer controlled. The required galvanic insulation between the PXI chassis and the controlling computer is ensured by an optical link.

The device under test (DUT) used for the development of the iSimulator is an LCR-meter model E4980EL de Keysight.

The other components, also visible on Fig. 3, are not used in this particular setup.

2.1.1 Connecting Box

The impedance Z_{CB} inside the connecting box is the key component that ensures the tractability of the generated reference impedance Z_{REF} . The determination of its resistance and phase angle is therefore required over the whole frequency range of interest.

The DC value of the resistance can be determined performing the well established calibration chain from the SI value of the ohm. The determination of the frequency dependence and the phase angle can be either calibrated by comparison to traceable standards or estimated by calculation if the design is sufficiently simple, as it is the case for coaxial geometry [3, 4].

Figure 4: a) Partial schematic of the connecting box showing the Manganin wire inside a Cu tube between the HC and LC connectors. The two wires used to measure the voltage drop, V_V , generated by the current I flowing through the wire are also represented. b) Picture of the practical realisation of the connecting box.

As represented in Fig. 4, the impedance is formed by a single Manganin wire of 0.5 mm of diameter located along the axis of a Cu tube of 5 mm of inner diameter, as represented in

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Fig 4 a). The current I , supplied by the internal oscillator of the DUT, is flowing along the wire from the connector HC to the connector LC. It then returns to the oscillator flowing into the opposite direction along the Cu tube forming the external conductor. With this current configuration, there is ideally no electromagnetic fields outside the coaxial line making the circuit insensitive to any external perturbations [5].

Two supplementary thin wires are soldered on the Manganin wire at the contact points A and B to allow the measurement of the voltage drop V_v generated by the current I . The distance of about 28 mm between the two points A and B determines the value of the resistance which is slightly above 100 mΩ. The frequency dependence of the resistance and the series inductance of the coaxial resistance between the two points A and B have to be determined either by calibration or by calculation from its geometric dimension and the properties of the used materials as described in [6].

A picture of the practical realisation of the connecting box is shown on Fig. 4 b). One can also see the star point connection of the outers of the HP and LP connectors. In such a way, the impedance of outer conductor (the Cu tube) is not a part of the impedance Z_{CB} as it is generally the case.

2.1.2 NI-PXI-4461 board

Figure 5: View of the NI PXI-4461 board with block diagrams of AI and AO channels [7].

A single NI-PXI-4461 board is used to both, generate the voltage signal S_v and to measured the voltage V_v and V_i needed to calculate the voltage ratio $V_r = V_v/V_i$. Figure 5 shows the board

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and the block diagrams of the AI and AO channels. More information on the specifications can be found here [7].

2.2 Software

Figure 6: Top: Front panel of the main LabView programme with three different parts A, B and C. Bottom: LabView code of the main program with the frequency loop.

A LabView programme is used to perform the measurement of the gain error and phase error of the DUT at different value of impedance (i.e. at different modulus and phases) and at different frequencies. The front panel and the LabView code are shown in Fig. 6. Three different parts can be distinguished in the front panel:

- In the part A, the the measured signals V_i and V_v are represented in the time domain and in the frequency domain. The absence of spectral leakage in the DFT of the V_i signal indicates the good synchronicity between the sampling frequency and the frequency of

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the internal oscillator of the DUT.

- The part B shows the time series of the real and imaginary part of Z_{REF} and Z_{DUT} being measured.
- In the part C, the mean value of Z_{REF} and Z_{DUT} that have been measured.

Aside these parts, the frequency, the identification of the used connecting box and the identification of the DUT are also visible.

3 Uncertainty components

As stated in the description of the working principle, the iSimulator allows the determination of the gain G_{DUT} of the DUT at a given frequency and for a given impedance amplitude and phase. The gain being given by Eq 1. However, it is well known that LCR-meter measurements can also be biased by an offset that has to be compensated by a short measurement (short compensation). Using the iSimulator, the short can easily be simulated adjusting the voltage source S_v to 0. In this case, the DUT is measuring $Z_{\text{DUT-s}}$. Even if V_r is in principle equal to zero some residual value V_{r-s} is observed due to unwanted inductive coupling and/or ground loop and the reference short impedance $Z_{\text{REF-s}} = Z_{\text{CB}}V_{r-s}$ has to be taken into account, especially when the gain is determined for low impedance value.

The effective gain of the DUT is then given by

$$G_{\text{DUT}} = \frac{Z_{\text{DUT}} - Z_{\text{DUT-s}}}{Z_{\text{REF}} - Z_{\text{REF-s}}} = \frac{Z_{\text{DUT}} - Z_{\text{DUT-s}}}{Z_{\text{CB}}(V_r - V_{r-s})} = (1 + g_{\text{DUT}})e^{j\varphi_{\text{DUT}}} \quad (3)$$

The gain and phase error of the DUT are then given by

$$\begin{cases} g_{\text{DUT}} = |G_{\text{DUT}}| - 1 \\ \varphi_{\text{DUT}} = \angle G_{\text{DUT}} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

3.1 DUT measurements

The uncertainties related to both real and imaginary parts of $Z_{\text{DUT}} = R_{\text{DUT}} + jX_{\text{DUT}}$ are only of type A. The impedance is measured N times and the mean value is calculated. As the type of noise present in a impedance measurement set has not been investigated, the uncertainty of the mean is given by standard deviation σ of the N values and not by $\sigma/\sqrt{(N)}$, as it would be in the case of white noise.

Therefore

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} R_{\text{DUT}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N R_k, \quad u(R_{\text{DUT}}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{k=1}^N (R_k - R_{\text{DUT}})^2} \\ X_{\text{DUT}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N X_k, \quad u(X_{\text{DUT}}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{k=1}^N (X_k - X_{\text{DUT}})^2}. \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

The same apply to the measurement of Z_{DUT}^s .

3.2 Reference resistance Z_{CB}

The resistance used in the connecting box CB is a resistance having a nominal value of 0.1Ω and its impedance can be represented the Eq. 6:

$$Z_{\text{CB}} = R_{\text{Nom}} \left[1 + d_{\text{DC}} + \alpha(f) \right] + j\omega L, \quad (6)$$

where d_{DC} is the relative deviation of the DC resistance from its nominal value, $\alpha(f)$ is a function describing the frequency dependence of the resistance and L is the residual series inductance. These three parameters have to be calibrated through a traceable calibration chain to the SI. The parameter d_{DC} depends generally on the time (drift), the current, the temperature and eventually the pressure or humidity. The two other parameters are more stable in time and barely dependent on ambient conditions. According the current CMCs, d_{DC} can easily be calibrated with an uncertainty ($k = 2$) of less than $1 \mu\Omega/\Omega$. $\alpha(f)$ can be evaluated with an uncertainty ($k = 2$) smaller than $100 \mu\Omega/\Omega$. The time constant of resistors can easily be calibrated with an uncertainty ($k = 2$) of 3 ns or smaller. That leads to an uncertainty on the inductance of 0.3 nH for a resistor $R = 0.1 \Omega$ ($u(L) = Ru(\tau)$).

Table 1 summarises the parameters of Z_{CB} with their uncertainties evaluated in the frequency range up to 5 kHz. To be conservative, the uncertainty on L has been significantly increased. Moreover, the uncertainty on d_{DC} has been significantly increased to take into account the drift ($10 \mu\Omega/\Omega$), the power effect for current up to 500 mA ($10 \mu\Omega/\Omega$) and the of 1 K of the temperature stability ($18 \mu\Omega/\Omega$).

3.3 Voltage ratio V_r

Two different analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) are used to simultaneously sample the voltage signals V_v and V_i . Each acquisition channel having its own gain error, the gain mismatch between the two channels has to be evaluated. Even if it is possible to calibrate the gain of each ADC channel individually [8, 9, 10], this calibration chain are quite time consuming and requires dedicated instruments (like Josephson voltage standard) not necessary available. Hopefully in our situation, the gain mismatch can also be evaluated repeating the measurement of G_{DUT} with the digitizers used to measure V_v and V_i reversed.

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Table 1: Parameters of the of the connecting box impedance Z_{CB} evaluated over the frequency range up to 5 kHz.

parameter	value	uncertainty ($k = 1$)	unit
R_{Nom}	0.1	-	Ω
d_{DC}	83722	23	$\mu\Omega/\Omega$
$\alpha(f)$	0	50	$\mu\Omega/\Omega$
L	14	10	nH

The measured voltage ratio \tilde{V}_r is therefore related to the "true" voltage ratio V_r by the factor $(1 + \Delta g)$. In the 'direct' configuration where the digitizer #1 is used to measure V_v and the digitizer #2 is used to measure V_i we have

$$\tilde{V}_r^d = \frac{\tilde{V}_v^d}{\tilde{V}_i^d} = \frac{(1 + g_1)V_v^d}{(1 + g_2)V_i^d} = (1 + \Delta g)V_r^d,$$

and therefore, according to Eq.3

$$G_{DUT}^d = (1 + g_{DUT})e^{j\varphi_{DUT}}(1 + \Delta g) = G_{DUT}(1 + \Delta g) \quad (7)$$

We are here considering that the gain mismatch Δg is the same for all voltage ratios (i.e. for both the voltage ratios V_r and V_{r-s}). This is true as long as each digitizer is working in its linear ranges, as it is the case here when the measured voltage is only a small fraction of the full range [10].

If the measurement is repeated with the digitizer reversed, i.e. the digitizer #2 is used to measure V_v and the digitizer #1 is used to measure by V_v we have

$$\tilde{V}_r^r = \frac{\tilde{V}_v^r}{\tilde{V}_i^r} = \frac{(1 + g_2)V_v^r}{(1 + g_1)V_i^r} = \frac{V_r^r}{(1 + \Delta g)},$$

and therefore

$$G_{DUT}^r = \frac{(1 + g_{DUT})e^{j\varphi_{DUT}}}{(1 + \Delta g)} = \frac{G_{DUT}}{(1 + \Delta g)} \quad (8)$$

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Combining Eq.7 and Eq.8 one obtains

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} G_{DUT} &= \sqrt{G_{DUT}^d G_{DUT}^r} \\ &= \frac{1}{Z_{CB}} \sqrt{\frac{(Z_{DUT} - Z_{DUT-s})^d (Z_{DUT} - Z_{DUT-s})^r}{(V_r - V_{r-s})^d (V_r - V_{r-s})^r}} \\ 1 + \Delta g &= \sqrt{\frac{G_{DUT}^d}{G_{DUT}^r}}. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (9)$$

With this procedure of repeating the measurement with the two ADC channels reversed, it is observed that the gain mismatch is independent of the frequency and reproducible with a Type B uncertainty of about $50 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$. Finally, the remaining uncertainty related to the voltage ratio measurement is the Type A uncertainty.

3.4 U-Budget

The total uncertainty budget has been evaluated using Metas.UncLin [11], a software library that facilitates the linear propagation of uncertainties through a measurement model.

The Fig. 7 shows the uncertainty on the gain error and on the phase error evaluated for different impedance value and at three frequencies: 20 Hz, 1 kHz and 10 kHz.

Figure 7: Uncertainty budget ($k=1$) for the gain error (on the left) and phase error (on the right) evaluated for three frequencies: 20 Hz, 1 kHz and 10 kHz. The dotted lines correspond to the Type B uncertainty, the dashed lines to the Type A uncertainty and the solid lines to the combined uncertainty.

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For impedance values well larger than $100\text{ m}\Omega$, the uncertainty budget is dominated by the Type B uncertainty (i.e. uncertainty on the impedance Z_{CB}) while for impedance values well smaller than $100\text{ m}\Omega$, it is the Type A uncertainty that is dominating the budget. The Type A uncertainty increases as $1/|Z|$ as the value of impedance decreases and it is ten times larger on the measurement of Z_{DUT} than on the measured voltage ratio V_r . The Type B uncertainty of the gain error is barely dependent on the frequency while the Type B uncertainty on the phase error linearly increases with the frequency.

It is worth to point out that the uncertainty on the gain error obtained using the iSimulator is between 10 and 100 times smaller than the specifications of the LCR-meter itself (E4980EL). Therefore, the characterisation of the LCR-meter using the iSimulator allows a significant improvement of the instrument's performances.

4 Validation

During the classical calibration procedure of an LCR-meter, the gain error and phase error of the instrument is obtained comparing the measured impedance Z_{DUT} to the traceable reference value Z_{REF} of the standard connected to the LCR-meter.

Figure 8: Gain error (left side) and phase error (right side) of the LCR-meter E4980EL measured either with the iSimulator or the classical calibration procedure using $1\text{ }\Omega$ and $10\text{ }\Omega$ resistance standards. The uncertainty bars correspond to $k=1$ uncertainty.

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Considering that the validation of the performances of the iSimulator can only be obtained for impedance values available for the classical calibration procedure. The validation has been performed for two resistance values: $1\ \Omega$ and $10\ \Omega$ over the whole frequency range of interest from 20 Hz to 10 kHz. Because the impedance inside the connecting box is resistor of $0.1\ \Omega$ the measured voltage ratio V_r where about 10 (for the calibration at $1\ \Omega$) and 100 (for the calibration of $10\ \Omega$).

As shown in Fig. 8, the results obtained using both calibration procedures are in agreement withing the $k=1$ uncertainty. Whatever the calibration procedure used, the gain error of this specific instrument is very small (well below $200\ \mu\Omega/\Omega$) and frequency independent. The uncertainty obtained for the phase error at frequencies equal or greater than 1 kHz is significantly larger for the iSimulator than for the classical procedure. This is related to the relatively large uncertainty ($\pm 10\ \text{nH}$) that has been attributed to the inductance L of Z_{CB} .

Figure 9: Absolute value of the measurement error ΔR of the LCR-meter E4980EL measured with the iSimulator at 1 kHz and for impedance value from $100\ \mu\Omega$ and $10\ \Omega$. As shown on the polar representation on the right, the phase angle of the impedance has been changed from $-90\ \text{deg}$ to $90\ \text{deg}$.

The ability of the iSimulator to calibrate the LCR-meter is not limited to few values along the real axis of the complex plan. Indeed, using the iSimulator, any impedance in the complex plan can be simulated. As represented on the polar plot on the right side of Fig. 9, a LCR-meter

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(model E4980EL) has been calibrated at 1 kHz and at different impedance ranging from $100 \mu\Omega$ to 10Ω and with phase angles between -90 deg and 90 deg .

The absolute value of the measurement error is represented on the left side of Fig. 9 for the different simulated impedance values. As it can be seen the measurement error is roughly constant and smaller than $10 \mu\Omega$ for simulated impedance smaller than $100 \text{ m}\Omega$ and then increase linearly with the modulus of the simulated impedance. The slope of this linear increasing corresponds to the gain error which is here of about $80 \mu\Omega/\Omega$.

The most interesting observation that can be done from the Fig. 9 is the fact that the measurement error (and also the gain error) is independent of the phase of the measured impedance! That means that, at least for this specific instrument, the gain error can be calibrated using resistance standards along the real axis of the complex plan and the results can then be extended to the whole impedance plan.

5 Conclusion

A new version of impedance simulator has been designed, developed and fully characterised using a commercial LCR-meter (Keysight, model E4980EL). The iSimulator can simulate impedance value from $100 \mu\Omega$ up to 10Ω with arbitrary phase angle. The $k=1$ uncertainty on the gain error is well below than the project's target uncertainty of 1 % for impedance value of $1 \text{ m}\Omega$. The uncertainty is even smaller than $100 \mu\Omega/\Omega$ for impedance value greater than $100 \text{ m}\Omega$. The iSimulator has been validate at frequencies from 20 Hz to 10 kHz. Thought, the iSimulator is supposed to be able to work at lower frequencies, 20 Hz is the lowest allowed frequency of the E4980EL instrument.

A JSON format

The results of the measurements as well as the measurement conditions are stored into a JSON data file. The JSON file is then processed through a MATLAB script to generate the final results with the uncertainty evaluation.

A.1 General Structure

The general structure of the JSON file is represented in Fig. A.1.

Figure A.1: General structure of the JSON file generated during the measurements and detailed structure of the information fields *PCinfo*, *Client*, *DUTinfo* and *REFinfo*.

All time stamps (like `startUTC` and `stopUTC`) are recorded in legal local time with a difference (offset) to the Universal Coordinated World Time (UTC) according the format from ISO 8601:2004. The field `PCinfo` contains information about the computer used and the LabView vi's name of the measurement program. The field `Client` gathers the information about the DUT's owner while `DUTinfo` contains the information about the DUT itself. Finally,

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REFinfo collect the information about the reference impedance hosted by the connecting box, Z_{CB} . The two remaining fields `direct` and `reverse` collect the raw results of the measurements performed in the *direct* and *reverse* configurations and have the same structure that is described in the following sub-section.

A.2 Measurements Result Structure

The detailed structure of the filed `direct` is shown in Fig. A.2. The structure of the field `reverse` is exactly the same.

Figure A.2: Structure of the measurement field *direct* and sub-fields *REF* and *DUT*.

In this example, the measurement has been performed at 4 different values of Z_{Nom} . `UTC` is the time stamp of each measurements, `Freq` is the frequency and `ZNom.R` and `ZNom.X` are respectively the nominal resistance and reactance. The temperature is measured at the beginning and at the end of the measurements of the four different values of `ZNom`. The field `Temperature` contains the mean value and the variation of the temperature during the measurement duration.

The field `DUT` is the raw results of the DUT's measurement. `Z.R` and `Z.stdR` are the mean and the Type A uncertainty of the measured resistance. `Z.X` and `Z.stdX` are the mean and the Type A uncertainty of the measured reactance. The field `Aux` collects the auxiliary information like the range of the instrument, the measuring current and voltage as well as the number of value measured for each setting of `ZNom`.

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The field **REF** is the raw results of the REF's measurement. **Vratio.A** and **Vratio.uA** are the mean and the Type A uncertainty of the real part of the voltage ratio. **Vratio.B** and **Vratio.uB** are the mean and the Type A uncertainty of the imaginary part of the voltage ratio. The field **Synch.correction** is the relative correction (in $\mu\text{Hz}/\text{Hz}$) applied to the external 10 MHz to make the sampling frequency synchronous with DUT's internal oscillator. The field **Synch.df** is the residual relative frequency offset (in $\mu\text{Hz}/\text{Hz}$) between the sampling frequency and the DUT's internal oscillator. Finally, **Voltages** gathers the modulus, the phase and the total harmonic content of the voltages V_i and V_v .

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